

Chemometric Investigation of Complex Equilibria in Solution Phase. Part-V. Correlation of Formation Constants of Manganese(II) or Zinc(II) Complexes of AADH/FAH with Co-solvent Characteristics

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The stoichiometric composition and extent of formation of the complex species formed in aquo-organic media in the interaction of Zn^{II} or Mn^{II} with AADH or FAH, is a multivariate chemical task. The primary data (pH versus volume of NaOH) under varying ratios of TLO to TMO and co-solvent content for each of the metal-ligand systems) was subjected to pre-processing to enhance the information to noise ratio. The initial approximate constants for protonated species, stoichiometric coefficients and a set of models to be tested were arrived by a heuristic approach. The MINQUAD 75 program having the advantages of steepest gradient, Marquardt algorithm was used to arrive at the best fit chemical model in each of the systems. The different trends in the distribution of the species (3D plots) under experimental variables (total concentrations of metal and ligand) are of practical utility in preparative chemistry to obtain optimum concentrations. The change in the number of water molecules associated with each of the equilibria is obtained by linear regression of transformed equation.

In yesteryears the analysis was limited to determination of total amount of metal ion/ligand/complex present in a drug, food/biological material/finished industrial product. Although the total Cd content in crab meat exceeds the toxic limit for human consumption, speciation studies established that only 2-3% is bio-available from gastrointestinal tract¹. This changed the facet of speciation (charge, stoichiometry and concentration of each of the species under a set of experimental condition, like dielectric constant, temperature, ionic strength, ingredient concentrations, matrix and interferences) studies from basic research to those pivotal in industry^{2,3} where many riddles like poor performance (or yield) and high reagent consumption were solved.

As the stoichiometric coefficients and stability constants of a chemical species are not directly measurable, the precision and accuracy have been greatly augmented with the advances in optimisation techniques^{4,5} and residual analysis⁶. The strides in development of instrumentation rendered it possible to ob-

tain data simultaneously from glass/ion selective electrodes/uv-visible spectrophotometer⁷, esr⁸ and nmr⁹ (¹⁵N/¹⁷O). Dimension reduction techniques like eigen vector decomposition and factor analysis¹⁰ found place in obtaining corroborative evidence for number of species present against simple crystallographic R test.

Acid hydrazides, in addition to their importance in pharmacy (isonicotinic acid hydrazide being a powerful anti-tubercular drug¹¹) find a key role in agriculture and synthesis of many organic compounds. Adipic acid dihydrazide (AADH is one of the constituents of coatings in epoxy resins in presence of Zn^{II} ¹², Cu^{II} ¹³, Ti^{IV} ¹⁴ or Fe^{II} ¹⁵ and in varnishes¹⁶ along with Mn^{II} , Pb^{II} or Co^{II} . Its use was recommended in improving the physical characteristics of latent hardeners, curing agents¹⁷ and semiconductor devices¹⁸. On the other hand, 2-furoic acid hydrazide (FAH) is one of the starting materials in the synthesis of low density foams¹⁰, fungicides²⁰ and nervous stimulants²¹. Although interest has hitherto been centered in exploiting the end-products in industry, biological materials etc., no

attempt has been made to elicit explicit knowledge to understand their role. Since *N,N'*-dimethylformamide (DMF) or dioxane (DOX) has been used in some of the chemical processes, a detailed investigation of species involved should be useful to employ optimum experimental conditions for desired characteristics of the products and to select most influential chemical parameters based on sensitivity analysis.

In continuation of our studies on development of chemical models for the interaction of a proton or divalent metal-ions with nitrogenous compounds (amino acids, peptides and hydrazides) in aquo-organic media²², the results of pH-metric studies on complexation of adipic acid dihydrazide (AADH) and 2-furoic acid hydrazide (FAH) with Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} in 10–60% water-*N,N'*-dimethylformamide/water-dioxane adopting a combination of Marquardt algorithm, Gauss-Newton and Steepest-descent methods are reported. The robustness of MINQUAD 75²³ for wild initial guess values of stability constants and precision and accuracy of the chemical models for errors in ingredient concentration and instrument noise are tested.

Chemical modelling :

AADH or FAH has two potential sites for metal coordination, namely, carbonyl oxygen and terminal amino nitrogen. However, the highest protonated form of the ligand as arrived from our earlier investigations²⁴ is LH⁺ in the case of FAH while LH₂²⁺ for AADH. Keeping in pace with popular algorithms in vogue for complex equilibria, we have considered the interaction of a metal ion with the ligand stripped of all labile protons in aqueous or aquo-organic media forming NB complexes. The formation constant for the *j*-th species for the equilibrium,

$$\beta_{m(j), l(j), h(j)} = \frac{[M_{m(j)}L_{l(j)}H_{h(j)}]}{FM_i^{m(j)}FL_i^{l(j)}FH_i^{h(j)}} \quad (2)$$

where FM_{*i*} and FL_{*i*} are the free concentrations of metal ion and ligand at *i*-th experimental point, *m*(*j*) and *l*(*j*) are the stoichiometric coefficients of metal ion and ligand and *h*(*j*) is negative for hydroxyl ions while

positive for protons. MINQUAD 75 employed in this study uses sum of the squares of the residuals in all the mass balance equations (*U*), given in equation (3),

$$U = \sum_{i=1}^{NP} (TME_i - TMC_i)^2 + (TLE_i - TLC_i)^2 + (THE_i - THC_i)^2 \quad (3)$$

as optimisation function. For example,

$$TMC_i = FM + \sum_{j=1}^{NB} m(j)\beta_{m(j)l(j)h(j)}FM_i^{m(j)}FL_i^{l(j)}FH_i^{h(j)} \quad (4)$$

is linear in stability constants and non-linear in free concentrations demanding iterative procedures to obtain shift vector in equilibrium constants.

$$[A^T A - H] \begin{bmatrix} S_c \\ S_\beta \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} g_c \\ g_\beta \end{bmatrix} [A^T * R] \quad (5)$$

where *A* and *H* are the matrices of first and second analytical derivatives of object function with respect to parameters to be refined, *R* is the residual vector, *S_c* and *S_β* are shifts in free concentrations (10⁻⁴ to 10⁻⁸) and overall equilibrium constants (10⁴ to 10³⁰) which are of widely different magnitudes.

Earlier experience with MINQUAD²⁵ wherein free concentrations and β_{*s*} were simultaneously refined led to inaccurate stability constants because of incompatibility in their numerical values. However, MINQUAD 75 which reduces failure of optimisation due to ill-conditioned matrix is adopted. Further, the present algorithm refines β instead of log β as the latter results in a highly non-concave and non-linear function which is difficult to be minimised by Gauss-Newton method. In fact the extreme over shifts experienced in SCOGS²⁶ were attributed to this limitation.

Species selection :

With the available mini-computers and limitations in optimisation procedures, exhaustive modelling is not a pragmatic method in complex equilibria even when the ligand is of LH₂ type. The maximum number of ligands bound per mole of metal ion (*n̄*) and the reactive forms of ligand in the pH region of metal com-

plex formation are obtained from SCPHD (2.0) [stability constant from pH-metric data]²² running on IBM compatible PC/XT under MS DOS 3.X or later versions. The prospective species to be considered in chemical modelling based on expert systems approach (SPEGEN-ml²⁷ written in T-prolog 2.0) are MLH, ML, M(LH)₂, ML₂H, ML₂, MLOH, ML₂OH for AADH, and ML, ML₂, MLOH, ML₂OH for FAH.

Refinement of stability constants :

Contrary to the popular belief that even wild guess constants should converge, detailed investigations by Sylva and Davidson²⁸, Larsson and Pardue²⁹ and by us³⁰ established the necessity of fairly good initial estimates in mathematically complex systems (more than two overlapping equilibria or ternary or quaternary systems). Otherwise the species may be rejected or the model leads to an ill-conditioned matrix. It should however be remembered that it is not the limitation of MINQUAD 75 alone but inherent in nonlinear programming in presence of minor species. We employed the formation constants of ML and ML₂ calculated by LIFSC³¹ (Lagrange interpolation for stability constants) and linear least-square analysis of pruned $\bar{n}$ data (SCPHD) as initial values for MINQUAD

75. The magnitudes of stability constants of unprotonated metal complexes and those for the proton-ligand complexes were used to obtain the guess constants for protonated and hydroxylated species.

Selection of best fit chemical model :

Since total number of models that are to be tested for M²⁺-AADH system $\left(\sum_{r=2}^n n c_r\right)$ in an exhaustive search are 502 preliminary screening for the presence of each of the species is performed which resulted in the species MLH, ML, ML₂H and ML₂. A species is rejected when the corresponding constant assumes a negative value or the SD of β is very high. However the rejected species were reconsidered after arriving at the best model.

The stability constants along with some of popular statistical parameters are incorporated in Table 1. Attempts are now in progress to develop algorithms for parallel processing which will render exhaustive modelling possible at least for selected systems on super-micros. In the present study, ML and ML₂ are considered in the base model and forward selection is used³² in which different models are generated by the addition of a new species. MODGEN-ml²⁷ in which there

TABLE 1—BEST FIT CHEMICAL MODELS WITH STATISTICAL PARAMETERS OF Mn^{II}-AADH OR -FAH IN AQUO-DMF (OR DOX)

%	log β_{mlh} (SD)				pH range	NE/NP	U/(NP-m)	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis	χ^2
	(v/v)	1 1 0	1 2 0	1 1 1								
<u>Mn^{II}-AADH (DMF)</u>												
0	1.306 (2)	—	4.675(6)	—	2.0-4.2	5/52	2.785 4	-12.169 8	3.545 3	-0.18	3.68	18.06
10	2.845(6)	—	6.909 (13)	—	2.4-4.2	3/25	10.477 2	-5.766 2	2.590 6	0.16	4.35	27.08
20	3.837 (17)	—	7.332 (18)	—	2.0-4.2	3/41	39.210 5	-2.031 2	1.625 7	-0.19	2.65	4.99
30	3.435 (4)	—	6.857 (15)	—	2.6-3.8	3/22	1.632 0	0.116 3	0.685 4	0.05	3.54	24.18
40	3.012(2)	—	6.675(30)	—	2.8-3.7	3/38	0.240 3	-3.958 4	0.381 0	-1.60	4.89	8.80
50	2.761(14)	—	6.459(9)	—	2.3-4.8	3/42	4.193 8	-1.796 8	3.627 4	-1.29	5.58	32.88
60	2.456(4)	—	6.088(27)	—	1.8-2.4	3/30	7.323 0	-1.798 6	2.093 4	0.26	2.89	6.73
<u>Mn^{II}-AADH (DOX)</u>												
10	1.815(6)	—	—	—	2.2-4.0	3/21	5.698 4	-7.192 4	2.576 8	-0.81	3.98	19.10
20	2.438(7)	—	—	—	2.2-4.0	3/22	6.785 4	-11.714 4	5.648 6	-1.21	5.16	22.20
30	2.038(6)	—	—	—	2.3-4.1	3/20	1.795 4	-10.981 4	4.647 8	-0.18	4.16	16.24
40	1.399(8)	—	—	—	2.3-4.0	3/22	11.562 9	-9.992 8	6.799 1	-0.95	4.98	29.56
50	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
60	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Table-1 (contd.)

<u>Zn^{II}-AADH (DMF)</u>												
0	2.449(4)	3.306(11)	5.305(7)	8.005(9)	1.8-4.0	5/131	1.745 5	-0.174 5	0.754 0	-0.92	6.95	70.04
10	2.619(10)	3.482(9)	5.739(18)	8.272(11)	1.8-4.2	3/86	72.457 8	-1.829 4	2.625 5	-0.78	3.62	11.82
20	2.922(5)	—	5.942(9)	8.550(12)	1.8-4.2	3/86	3.373 5	-4.018 2	4.165 9	-0.32	4.62	15.02
30	2.342(8)	—	5.762(6)	8.329(33)	2.2-6.0	3/31	3.083 5	-1.214 8	0.963 5	-0.12	4.12	46.78
40	2.107(4)	—	5.267(6)	8.186(8)	1.93-2.6	3/83	98.921 3	0.791 4	2.012 9	0.58	2.95	48.09
50	1.905(7)	—	4.982(8)	8.081(16)	2.3-4.9	3/42	3.993 9	-2.958 4	2.516 3	-1.70	6.67	22.88
60	1.842(15)	—	4.773(21)	7.902(12)	1.8-6.0	3/82	7.213 9	-2.256 6	1.875 6	-2.36	4.63	64.96
<u>Zn^{II}-AADH (DOX)</u>												
10	2.406(10)	4.949(7)	5.769(8)	8.241(9)	1.8-6.0	3/71	1.285 5	-3.647 1	1.567 8	0.03	3.39	38.36
20	2.574(5)	5.836(7)	5.411(35)	8.668(31)	1.8-6.0	3/65	12.825 4	9.291 0	2.657 6	-0.19	2.00	16.76
30	2.751(2)	5.083(6)	4.544(5)	8.061(3)	1.8-6.0	3/73	0.625 5	-14.926 0	2.657 8	0.47	4.73	54.76
40	2.740(30)	4.715(15)	3.877(21)	7.635(12)	1.8-6.0	3/69	6.404 9	3.110 4	1.137 2	1.27	2.16	31.06
50	2.153(3)	3.567(6)	3.612(6)	7.216(5)	1.6-6.0	3/86	4.134 5	-5.456 9	3.152 0	1.35	5.93	14.99
<u>Zn^{II}-FAH (DMF)</u>												
0	2.186(4)	4.002	—	—	1.7-3.0	5/57	0.466 6	-4.918 1	-2.899 9	-0.20	3.43	46.63
10	2.624(9)	4.242(10)	—	—	2.2-4.2	3/33	12.625 6	3.019 5	1.956 6	0.98	3.78	26.98
20	2.950(12)	4.628(8)	—	—	2.0-6.0	3/52	31.565 3	-3.786 3	3.149 8	-0.91	3.70	8.31
30	3.175(6)	4.915(9)	—	—	2.0-3.2	3/43	27.413 7	-2.368 9	2.850 0	-0.65	3.20	12.36
40	3.369(22)	5.175(18)	—	—	2.0-3.2	3/45	26.188 9	-3.263 6	2.854 4	0.82	3.40	13.68
50	3.447(6)	5.377(3)	—	—	2.3-3.1	3/25	13.886 8	-2.319 0	2.596 2	-0.71	2.95	14.92
60	2.440(17)	4.518(15)	—	—	2.0-2.4	3/21	9.773 9	-1.327 2	2.894 4	-0.29	3.11	1.48
<u>Zn^{II}-FAH (DOX)</u>												
10	2.934(7)	—	—	—	1.8-3.0	3/53	2.241 0	-3.048 5	2.182 7	-0.39	2.70	5.28
20	2.395(5)	—	—	—	1.8-2.8	3/41	5.833 4	-0.753 6	1.342 5	6.13	3.64	13.26
30	2.168(10)	—	—	—	1.8-2.6	3/35	26.609 6	-1.247 3	2.847 7	0.50	4.81	12.71
40	1.986(20)	—	—	—	1.8-2.3	3/27	37.180 5	0.242 1	3.319 1	0.01	3.57	28.73
50	1.756(12)	—	—	—	1.7-2.2	3/33	37.187 2	-1.381 4	3.356 9	0.04	3.81	10.66
<u>Mn^{II}-FAH (DMF)</u>												
0	2.170(9)	—	—	—	2.0-4.0	5/39	2.134 0	-5.338 6	0.993 3	-0.59	4.36	31.56
10	2.609(12)	—	—	—	1.8-4.0	3/27	36.453 2	2.264 1	3.286 5	-0.55	4.02	11.74
20	2.871(6)	—	—	—	2.0-4.0	3/26	10.209 8	-0.437 5	1.735 1	-0.63	2.95	15.13
30	3.015(9)	—	—	—	2.15-2.6	3/20	29.275 1	-2.002 8	2.878 3	-0.88	4.15	1.33
40	2.836(8)	—	—	—	2.0-2.8	3/22	0.568 6	0.603 8	4.046 2	1.12	6.24	22.73
50	2.625(6)	—	—	—	2.3-2.7	3/17	63.847 4	-2.107 4	4.186 5	-0.39	2.25	4.06
60	2.271(14)	—	—	—	2.0-2.28	3/21	3.460 4	-0.677 1	1.722 2	-0.20	2.74	2.24
<u>Mn^{II}-FAH (DOX)</u>												
10	2.821(9)	—	—	—	1.8-2.6	3/32	23.277 6	-0.858 3	2.651 7	0.15	3.62	7.33
20	2.330(5)	—	—	—	2.0-3.0	3/37	5.981 1	-1.592 0	1.353 5	-0.46	3.86	7.41
30	2.011(13)	—	—	—	1.8-2.2	3/23	11.275 9	0.145 5	1.807 9	0.26	3.33	15.99

NE = No. of experiments; NP = total no. of points in NE experiment; m = no of equilibria; mean, SD, Skewness, Kurtosis and χ^2 are for the residuals.

is an option even for developing models with backward elimination wherein species are successively eliminated from the model with highest number of species (4 in the present case) is employed.

Residual analysis :

The software available in this field yields statistical parameters (Table 1) but selection of best fit model is a matter of subjective decision. The knowledge base²⁷ incorporating thumb rules (heuristics) based on earlier reports and our own experience is partially used in this investigation. The best fit model for each metal-ligand system in all compositions of aquo-organic mixtures are described in Table 1. Crystallographic *R* factor test which indicates the appropriateness of inclusion of complexes in the model is employed. As the numerical values of *U* corrected for degrees of freedom and *R* for models with 2, 3 and 4 species decrease continuously, the last one was found to be appropriate. Corroborative evidence of the four species model was obtained from the fact that the simulated titration curve progressively approaches the experimental one as the number of species increased from lowest number. However there is no scope for the over-ambitious modelling which is evident from the deviations of pH_{cal} for experimental data are greater than the accuracy of the system. When the species rejected in the preliminary modelling were introduced at this stage, no improvement in the fit was observed or they were rejected in some cases.

The χ^2 values range between ≈ 2 and ≈ 70 which are less than $\chi^2_{\nu,0.5}$ indicating that unweighted residuals follow a part of normal distribution. In equilibrium chemistry this statistics has become popular only recently and values approximately 10 to 400 were reported for chemical equilibria of increasing complexity (acid-basic equilibria to quaternary metal-ligand complexes)³³. Very small values of standard deviation (2.6578×10^{-4}) and mean deviation (-14.921×10^{-5}) for a typical system (Zn-AADH in 30% DOX) furnishes corroborative evidence for the normal distribution. However, values of kurtosis and skewness are higher than those expected for normal distribution (3.0 and 0.0 respectively). Hence, the confidence contours of $\log \beta_s$ which can be calculated from Table 1

will be only approximate. This is as a result of correlation of $\log \beta_s$ and the trend of residuals is slightly perturbed from normal distribution. In fact standard deviation in β reflects realistic errors than that in $\log \beta$ as the two quantities are related by the equation,

$$\sigma(\log \beta) = \sigma(\beta)/(2\beta). \quad (6)$$

Effect of errors on metal-ligand equilibria:

The stability constant of ML species is rather insensitive to errors in $\log \beta_{\text{oth}}$ as is evident from Table 2. However MLH is either rejected during refinement or results in very large error (1 log unit) implying the need for very accurate values of stability constants of proton-ligand complexes. Further under unfavourable conditions simultaneous refinement will result in spurious models, although the statistics appear to be fair (Table 3).

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ERROR IN PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS ON $\log \beta_{i,l,h}$ OF Zn^{II} -AADH-30% DOX SYSTEM

Error introduced in PL	$\Delta \log \beta$				$U/(NP-m) \times 10^8$
	1 1 0	1 2 0	1 1 1	1 2 1	
+3SD	-0.010	-0.214	-0.663	-0.171	0 094 8
-3SD	0.009	0.176	Rejected	0.149	0 095 0
+1SD	-0.009	-0.091	-0.429	-0.066	0 089 0
-1SD	-0.004	0.042	-0.011	0.047	0 089 7
-1%	0.057	0.383	Rejected	0.325	0 136 5
+1%	0.012	-0.428	-0.987	-0.401	0 126 1
+2%	0.109	-0.759	-1.331	-0.715	0 302 7
-2%	0.150	0.915	Rejected	0.692	0 296 2

TABLE 3—SIMULTANEOUS REFINEMENT OF PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS (Zn^{II} -AADH-30%-DOX SYSTEM)

<i>m l h</i>	$\log \beta_{m,l,h}$	
	Simultaneous	$\log \beta_{\text{oth}}$ fixed
0 1 1	3.507 1 (0.01)	3.507
0 1 2	6.130 0 (0.01)	6.126
1 1 0	2.748 0 (0.02)	2.751 (0.02)
1 1 1	4.690 0 (0.43)	4.344 (0.05)
1 2 0	5.118 0 (0 11)	5.083 (0.06)
1 2 1	8.121 0 (0.20)	8.061 (0 03)

TABLE 4—RETRIVEL OF PROTON-LIGAND CONSTANTS FROM METAL-LIGAND DATA (Zn^{II}-AADH-30% DOX)

<i>m l h</i>	Retrieved β 's	P-L data
0 1 1	3.506 (0.001)	3.507 (0.06)
0 1 2	6.125 (0.001)	6.126 (0.06)
1 1 0	2.751	
1 1 1	4.344	
1 2 0	5.083	
1 2 1	8.061	

In an attempt to check whether any chemical equilibria resulting in change of hydrogen ion concentration are omitted in arriving at the best fit model, $\log \beta_{oih}$ are refined keeping those corresponding for metal-ligand complexes fixed. The excellent agreement (Table 4), though rarely occurs, between the retrieved values with those obtained from independent proton-ligand experiments, shows very clearly that no other equilibria which are proton-sensitive are ignored.

A study of the effect of systematic errors of different magnitudes up to pessimistic limits in the concentration of EO, ALK, TLO and TMO is made adopting factorial design. A perusal of 3D-plots and surface contours (Fig. 1) reveals that errors in EO and ALK have pronounced effect than those in TLO and TMO. Further, even very large errors in initial total volume VO which is important in understanding the effect of mixing volumes and pK_w have been found to have a little effect. Since the errors in the ingredient concentration in the present investigation are less than 1%, the chemical model proposed is accurate.

Distribution plots :

The protometric titration plots for the interaction of FAH or AADH with proton or Zn^{II}/Mn^{II} in aqueous/aquo-organic (DMF/DOX) media show a single buffer region in the pH range of 2.0–3.5 for FAH and 2.0–4.5 for AADH. The task of parameter ($\log \beta$) estimation in these cases is complicated as the number of equilibria increased due to the simultaneous formation of proton-ligand as well as metal-ligand complexes in a narrow range of pH region. Under these conditions it results only in minimisation of error, sum of squares by internal adjustment of the stability con-

Fig. 1. 3D-plots and surface contours of $\Delta \log \beta_{11h}$ with errors in ingredient concentrations and total volume.

stants by the optimisation procedure. Thus in absence of the availability of reliable $\log \beta$'s for some of the equilibria by independent procedures, only the sum of the stability constants is acceptable. We have partially achieved this goal by fixing the proton-ligand constants while refining those for metal ligand.

The reactive forms of AADH are LH and LH₂ while that for FAH being LH in the pH region of metal

complexation resulting in the possibility of detection of $M(LH)_n$ in addition to ML_n species by pH metry in the former case only.

For AADH ·

For FAH

Above equations represent the formation of different metal complexes wherein changes in solvation and aquation in mixed solvent media are omitted for simplicity.

Considerable decrease/increase of percentage or absence of a species in presence of a co-solvent (DMF/DOX) with different amount are in fact manifestation of the cumulative effect of several solute-solvent and solvent-solvent processes. Since it is difficult to probe into the constituent terms for $\Delta G^{\ddagger}$, work is in progress for determining single ion free energy transfer of some of the species.

Sensitivity analysis of percentage of metal complex species : In order to understand the effect of errors in logarithm of formation constants versus the percentage distribution of various species, a few typical computer runs were performed by introducing systematic errors of different magnitude ($\pm 3SD$ to $\pm 5\%$) (Fig. 2)

in the best fit chemical models. It was observed that 3SD limits have little effect on the species concentration (not shown in the figure) indicating the validity of the distribution plots. However errors of higher magnitude although do not change the trend, results in considerable deviation which warrants a careful scrutiny of reported formation constants under different conditions to adopt them in other field of research (total parenteral nutrition, toxicity studies, biological activity) wherein either free metal ion concentration and/or complexed species are of vital importance.

Fig. 2. Effect of errors in $\log \beta_{110}$ on the distribution of species on a function of pH.

Solute-solvent interactions :

Although the use of water-miscible co-solvents was to increase the solubility of organic ligands with high hydrophobic moieties, the fact that no solvent is truly inert led to intensive investigations of rate and equilibrium studies in mixed solvent media. A perusal of the formation constants of complexes of AADH/FAH with Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} in 10–60% (v/v) DOX or DMF shows a non-linear change with solvent composition. It is clear that both electrostatic and non-electrostatic factors of varying magnitudes are responsible for the cumulative effect.

The values of $\log K^M$ vs n_x were analysed by orthogonal polynomial method developed by Forsythe³⁴.

A quadratic trend (Fig. 3) was found to be sufficient based on statistics of the model equation and visual pattern. This empirical model, although does not have any sound theoretical basis, is useful to predict the equilibrium constants of ligands in the homologous series or in the presence of co-solvents of similar characteristics.

Fig. 3. Variation of $\log \beta_{110}$ with mole fraction (n_x) by orthogonal polynomial fit

Correlation of $\log K^M$ with functions of (H_2O) :

McBryde³⁵ rationalised apparently different models proposed for variation of equilibrium constants of neutral (phenols, carboxylic acids) and cationic (ethylene diamine) acids considering the number of water as well as solvent molecules released as a result of different solvating properties of the species involved in the equilibrium. The changes in transfer free energy (ΔG^1) for the process,

from water to aquo-organic medium of specific composition is given by,

TABLE 5—LINEAR TREND ANALYSIS OF $\log ([H_2O]/[S])$ VERSUS $j \log [S] + \log k^m$ FOR Zn^{II} -AAADH IN DMF MEDIA

J	Slope	SD	CCC	SI	FEHR
-5	3.605 7	0.222 8	0.980 6	0.022 7	0.127 2
-4	2.893 6	0.191 8	0.977 7	0.026 0	0.136 3
-2	2.181 6	0.161 3	0.972 4	0.032 2	0.151 8
-1	0.757 5	0.103 6	0.910 5	0.104 5	0.273 2
0	0.045 5	0.078 8	-0.113 9	1.293 6	0.963 5
+1	-0.666 6	0.061 3	0.957 8	0.049 2	0.187 5
+2	-1.378 6	0.058 2	0.990 9	0.010 7	0.087 3
+3	-2.090 6	0.071 4	0.094 0	0.007 0	0.087 3
+4	-2.802 7	0.094 2	0.994 2	0.006 8	0.069 6
+5	-3.514 7	0.121 4	0.993 9	0.007 2	0.071 6

0.00 < SI < 0.02 and FEHR < 0.10 indicate best fit of the model. CCC = Corrected correlation coefficient = $1 - (NP-1) (RSS/TSS) / (NP-2)$; SI = exner parameter = $(RSS / [(NP-2) TSS])^{1/2}$; FEHR = Ebreusen parameter = $(RSS / TSS)^{1/2}$; RSS = residual sum of squares = $\sum_{i=1}^{NP} (y_{obs(i)} - y_{cal(i)})^2$; TSS = total sum of squares = $\sum_{i=1}^{NP} (y_{obs(i)} - y_{mean})^2$.

$$(j \log [S] + \log K_{ML}^M) - \log K_{ML}^W =$$

$$\frac{\Delta G^1}{2.303 RT} - w \log ([H_2O]/[S]) + j \log [H_2O]_M \quad (12)$$

which contains two unknown parameters w (number of water molecules) and j ($= w + s$ where s is number of solvent molecules). Of the various regression equations with j values from -5 to $+5$, the one with minimum SD, and maximum correlation coefficient corrected for degrees of freedom is considered. Although Table 5 incorporates the values of j , w and s for the chemical systems investigated in this study, it is difficult to unequivocally conclude whether solvent (H_2O or co-solvent) molecules are released only from the primary solvation shell or include those from the disordered zone. Yet the increase in solubility, changes in $\log K^M$ with n_x and functions of $[H_2O]$ indicate specific solute-solvent interactions playing a definite role in metal chelate formation.

Robustness of MINIQAD 75 :

When the initial approximate stability constants of

Zn^{II} -AADH (30% DOX) are 0.5 log units greater than those obtained in the best fit model, one of the species (MLH) is rejected although the other constants are nearer to the true values. On the other hand, when the constants are less by 0.5 units, $\log \beta_{111}$ differs by 0.3 units and other constants agree very well. Our earlier studies indicated that even in the case of proton-ligand complexes with two equilibria ($\log K_1 < \log K_2$) algorithm plays an important role. This is because the valid range of initial constants extends from $\log K + 0.5$ (Gauss-Newton algorithm) to $\log K + 3$ units (steepest gradient + Gauss-Newton + Marquardt employed in MINIQAD 75). The safe area was further extended to $\log K$ (approximate) = $\log K$ (true) + 5.0 units in the case of AADH ($\log K_1 > \log K_2$) indicating the importance of nature of equilibria even when the same algorithm is used (Fig. 4). To sum up, the robustness in complex equilibria depends on (i) algorithm, (ii) complexity of the system (proton-ligand to quaternary complexes), (iii) number of simultaneous equilibria, (iv) optimisation function and (v) whether $\log K_i$ is greater than $\log K_{i+1}$ or not.

Fig. 4 Safe limits of initial estimates of $\log \beta_{11b}$ convergence with MINIQAD 75: (a) Zn^{II} -FAH (40% DMF) and (b) Zn^{II} -AADH (30% DOX).

Experimental

Aqueous solutions (0.1 mol dm^{-3}) of AADH and FAH (Fluka AG) were prepared in doubly glass-distilled deionised water. Zinc(II) chloride was prepared from zinc granules (AnalaR) and manganese(II) chloride (E. Merck, pro-analyti) was used. All other chemi-

cals were of A.R. grade. 'A' grade glassware was used throughout, DMF (E. Merck) was purified by preliminary drying over molecular sieves³⁶ followed by fractional vacuum distillation³⁷ since the solvent decomposed at its boiling point. The purity of the sample was tested against the reported standard resistance ($>10000 \Omega$) and refractive index (1.48)^{38,39}. DOX (E. Merck) was purified by refluxing over KOH and dried on BaO according to the reported procedure⁴⁰.

Standardisation of ingredient and calibration of the instrument: As the formation constants of metal-ligand species are complex implicit functions of errors in ingredient concentrations, derived parameters like the correction factor for glass electrode, pK_w , the pessimistic errors in the preparation of ligand solutions were calculated by COSWT (Concentration Of Solution by WeighT method)⁴¹ written in MS Fortran. Typical results indicate that the error in ligand solution is less than 0.2%. The random errors arising in the determination of concentration of NaOH were assessed by COST⁴¹ (Concentration Of Solution by Titrimetry) employing analysis of variance of one way classification. The F value (1.567) indicated good precision of titrimetric results incommensurate with the accuracy of the data acquisition system.

The equilibration of glass electrode and details of titration assembly were described by us earlier²². Testing the linearity of response of the glass electrode by two buffer solutions involved inaccuracies. Hence, it was used only for initial setting⁴² and Gran analysis of titration data of the strong acid against strong base was performed⁴³. Further, there is relevance of the use of laboratory robots even for pseudo-automation⁴⁴ of the task of complex equilibria.

*Experimental design for complex equilibria (CEED)*⁴⁵: The confidence contours of stability constants resulting from any algorithm depend on the choice of the objective function used in optimisation and convergence criteria but also on the distribution of residuals. In order to improve the signal-to-noise ratio, attempts were made to enhance the concentrations of minor species by choosing different ratios of metal-to-ligand concentrations ($TLO/TMO = 2$ to 5, vide Table 6).

TABLE 6—TOTAL INITIAL CONCENTRATIONS OF INGREDIENTS

Titrand : TMO $[Mn^{II}] = 2.968 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Titrand : TMO $[Zn^{II}] = 3.146 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 0.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, VO = 50.0 cm^3 , Temp = 301 K

EO = 21.85 $\times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Titrand : NaOH = 0.390163 mol dm^{-3}
TLO/ $10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Co-solvent DMF/DOX % (v/v)	DMF		DOX		TMO:TLO
	AADH	FAH	AADH	FAH	
0.0	5.982	6.035			1 : 1
	7.976	8.048			1 : 2
	9.970	10.059			1 : 3
	14.955	15.089			1 : 5
	19.940	20.119			1 : 6
10.0	5.985	6.002	6.030	5.912	1 : 2
	9.986	10.005	10.051	9.854	1 : 3
	14.964	15.007	15.076	14.781	1 : 5
20.0	6.161	6.067	6.030	6.061	1 : 2
	10.270	10.111	10.051	10.101	1 : 3
	15.400	15.167	15.076	15.152	1 : 5
30.0	6.161	5.797	6.136	6.150	1 : 2
	10.269	9.662	10.227	10.250	1 : 3
	15.403	14.493	15.141	15.375	1 : 5
40.0	6.160	5.797	6.136	6.034	1 : 2
	10.270	9.662	10.227	10.057	1 : 3
	15.400	14.493	15.341	15.086	1 : 5
50.0	6.160	5.894	6.441	6.056	1 : 2
	10.270	9.823	10.736	10.094	1 : 3
	15.400	14.736	16.104	15.140	1 : 5
60.0	5.953	5.973	6.111	6.061	1 : 2
	9.922	9.056	10.186	10.101	1 : 3
	14.883	14.933	15.279	15.152	1 : 5

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